

ARTS

HISTORY OF THE AUCTION SALES OF THE ART WORKS DESCENDED FROM THE RUSSIAN IMPERIAL AND PRIVATE COLLECTIONS AT THE WESTERN-EUROPEAN AUCTIONS IN 1928-1935 YY

Bezgubova (Sklyaeva) A.A.

Research associate of the St. Petersburg Branch of the Archive of the Russian Academy of Sciences

Abstract

Author sets the task to trace the history of the auction sales of the Russian art heritage abroad in the 1920-1930 yy.. The process of nationalization of the cultural heritage started after October of 1917th and it was continued by the foundation of a number of institutions, particular "Commission for the acquisition of antiquarian and artistic values for the sale abroad" (1921), "Gostorg" (1925, transformed in "Antikvariat (1928)) which were allowed to collect and to sold the nationalized heritage. The article could shed some light on the chronology of the Soviet decrees and the appearance of these organizations.

Keywords: art collections, nationalization, history of the auctions, nationalization of the collections, nationalization of cultural heritage, Soviet cultural politic, Soviet-German relations, Soviet decrees

The beginning of the era of immense sales of cultural heritage can be attributed to June 1, 1921, when the Commission for the acquisition of antiquarian and artistic values for the sale abroad was formed. So the nationalization of private property, which began immediately after the October Revolution of 1917: palaces, mansions and collections, received a rush legislative justification by the Soviet authorities.

The authorities apprehended the threat of the lack of control over the movement of valuables, as well as their looting, and therefore in June 1918 they established first the Department for Museums and the Protection of Monuments of Art and Antiquities of the People's Commissariat of Education (Otdel po delam muzeyev i okhrany pamyatnikov iskusstva i stariny Narkompros) (May 28, 1918), and then the Commission for the Protection and Registration of Monuments of Art and Antiquities (Komissiya po okhrane i registratsii pamyatnikov iskusstva i stariny) (June 1918). In the same post-revolutionary year, the first decrees on the loss of the right to private property (mansions palaces, factories) appeared, the prohibition of the export of objects of special artistic value abroad (September 22, 1918), amongst of them was "On Registration, Registration and Preservation of Monuments art and antiquities that were in the possession of individuals, societies and institutions" (October 5, 1918). In January 1919, a new organization appeared, the National Museum Fund of the General Science of the People's Commissariat of Education of the RSF. In January 1919, the State Museum Reserve (Gosmuseifond) of the Glavnauka under the People's Commissariat of Enlightenment of RSFSR (Narkompros) (Natsional'nij muzeynij fond Glavnauki Narkompros RSFSR) was created. Its tasks were to manage the selection and to redistribute the confiscated valuables (until November 1927); and in June 1, 1929 the Leningrad department of Gosmuzejfond was liquidated. This organization was involved in the registration and distribution of nationalized items – 1,375 private collections were registered from 1918

to 1927.

After all the era of sales was started by V.I. Lenin's order concerning the sale of the Romanoff' jewels and regalia. Previously these treasures were stored in the Winter Palace's Diamond Room, and were sold in London in October 1922, Amsterdam (November 1922, April 1923), Stockholm (April 1923), in Paris (March 1924). In October 1926 they were bought by Norman Weiss in London and in March 1927 were sold at the sales of Christie's devoted to the sales of the Diamond fund of USSR.

According to the report by M.D. Filosofov on the inventory of April 2, 1929, from 1917 to 1928, the Hermitage received 5,480 paintings. [1, p. 10]

In 1925, under the Narkomtorg, another institution was set up: the State import and export trading office of the State Import-Export Trading Office of the RSFSR (Gosudarstvennaja importno-eksportnaya trgovaya kontory Gostorga RSFSR) (Gostorg), which was transformed in 1928 into the main office Gostorg - "Antikvariat", which was given the privilege of import and export trade (by the order of Glavnauka the liquidated repositories of the State Museum Reserve (Gosmuzejfond) in Moscow and Leningrad were distributed between the country's museums and the State Import-Export Trading Office of the RSFSR (Gosfond) and the "Antikvariat"). By the time of liquidation of the Leningrad department of the State Museum Reserve (Gosmuzejfond), until June 1, 1929 – 51,271 items had been transferred to their main office and "Antikvariat".

At the end of 1927, the 15th Congress established a 5-year plan for the export of antiquities, and in February 1928 the first steps were taken to select objects and antiquities for export purposes in museums.

The functions of the selection of works for export in March 1929 took over the Subcommittee under the Government Commission L.M. Khinchuk, People's Commissar of Domestic Trade of the USSR. At first 2,200 pictures were selected by this Subcommittee, but as a result, by June 1929, 1,950 paintings were moved

to the warehouses of the 'Antikvariat' (formerly - Gostorg). [1, p. 17] According to the article of today's researcher - Julia Kantor, using the State Hermitage Museum's archival documents the Hermitage received 2,880 paintings. Among them 350 were the works of considerable artistic value, 59 – the masterpieces of world significance, 11 of them returned to the State Hermitage Museum, fortunately, not finding a buyer. [3, 4, p. 22, 475-492]

Works, which for one reason or another did not interest "Antikvariat" for export purposes, were transferred to them in the State Import-Export Trading Office of the RSFSR, i.e. for domestic trade or for distribution to Soviet museums. In 1919 the newspaper 'Art of the Commune' ('Iskusstvo Kommuni') announces the idea of exchanging "rembrandts for tractors." And in 1920, this message was picked up by the masses, as well as by the leading statesmen, in particular by M.A. Gorky (in 1919-1921 he was a chairman of the Petrograd Expert Commission by formation of the Export values fund).

Further series of decrees and resolutions, the organization of new institutions responsible for the appraisal of the values, their distribution and exporting is a quite complicated episode which testifies an unavoidable state total program of the sales of the heritage for the purpose of a new Soviet state's currency reserve replenishment.

In June 16, 1922 in Rapallo was signed the Soviet-German agreement on the restoration of diplomatic relations and trade and economic relations, which also provides an impetus for sales of the antique heritage concentrated in the warehouses of Gokhran (State Depository of Valuables). In October 1923 the Soviet government concluded an agreement with the Berlin auction firm 'Kunstauktionhaus Rudolph Lepke' which implicated obtaining 7.5% of the value of the company and 25% of their profits on sales. The terms of the contract with Lepke's seemed very beneficial to Soviet politicians, because the company undertook to independently provide half of the sums for purchases, as well as to do packing and transportation.

It should be noted that trade diplomatic relations with other countries will state later: with Great Britain and France – in the course of 1924.

1926 year became a kind of frontier when the policy of industrialization of the country concerned both a common citizen and any organization of the country. So, at the beginning of that year, the property of the royal suburban residences was exported. All museums of the Soviet country received instructions on the sale of unnecessary and dilapidated property and at the end of the year - the property of suburban palace-museums was offered for export sale. And in 1927, the People's Commissariat of Enlightenment (Narkompros), dealing with issues of culture (an analogue of the today's Ministry of Culture), ruled the export plan for antiques - for half a million rubles.

Germany became the main market for Russian cultural heritage sold by the Soviet government within a short period, marked the active period of the first state five-year plan (1928-1932) of the accumulation of currency reserve for industrialization of the USSR. And

the auction house Lepke was the first who made a treaty with the soviet powers at first about the purchasing at the USSR's art market (autumn of 1923) and then about the sales of the works of arts from the Hermitage and the Gosmuzejfond storing also there (autumn of 1927). [5, p. 240]

Only in the autumn of 1927 Lepke's reported about his readiness to start the auction from suburban residences-museums. At the time, 139,615 units were transferred to the commission of the State Museum Reserve (Gosudarstvennij Muzejnij fond). This, in fact, was a signal that not only the royal crowns and church values from Gokhran and private collections, but also items from the museum expositions and the storages, were going to be sold under the hammer.

In Moscow, the Commission on the selection of items for sale abroad, which included representatives of the Armory Chamber, Gostorg and The State Historical Museum was created.

However, the whole historical tussle with the sale of antiquarian and cultural values had until 1928 the nature of the behind-the-scenes play of the Soviet government, when small lots of values were sold, and individual tycoons could buy them after certain diplomatic arrangements.

Whereas, starting with the Berlin auction of Rudolph Lepke on November 6-7, 1928 (where items from the Mikhailovsky Palace, Gatchina and the Hermitage were sold) (Fig. 1), the game could no longer remain unnoticed, becoming too obvious for all tactics of the young Soviet state.

The organization "Antikvariat" - in fact, a subsidiary of the People's Commissariat for Foreign Trade, which has tremendous leverage on the Narkompros.

On June 4-5, 1929, the Lepke's auction house organized the 2nd auction of works from the Russian collections. The remains from the State Import-Export Trading Office: the works of the Mikhailovsky Palace, the Sheremetev's, Stroganoff's, Menshikov's palace museums and others were presented at this auction. Only works which were sold at "average" prices were found by buyers, among them: the oil study "Maria with kind" by Titian "with inaccurate attribution", "Venetian landscape" by F. Guardi, "Portrait of Prince Elector Frederick the Wise of Saxony" by L. Cranach. These significant items did not find their buyers: bust of Houdon, two portraits of Levitsky's brush, paintings by C.J. Vernet, "Jesus Christ" by H. van Rembrandt, "St. Hieronymus" by Titian, "The Entombment" by P. P. Rubens.

The "pre-auction" period of the "Antikvariat" demanded the recognition of the museum works, sometimes taken from the exhibitions, as "not an asset of museum significance", as "the state funds of non-museum value". In this status they moved by sea to Stettin (then – Germany; from 1945 - Poland), then by rail - to Berlin and at customs these passed to the representatives of the collector Gaoulust Gulbekyan.

According to statistics of the People's Commissariat for Foreign Trade (called Narkomvneshtorg or Vneshtorg), compiled on the basis of documents of 1918-40s, 187,000 of "paintings and other art objects" were allocated for export by various organizations. [6,

p. 5; 7, p.120] At the same time it is known that the 'Antikariat' controlled the sales of near about 1,000 pictures abroad (not accounting the works of applied arts; concerning of this sum see below). Famous scientist researching the history of the Soviet art sales gives

another number – 1,450, but according to the published lists of the returning pictures to the State Hermitage in 1931-1937 this number should be changed for 1000 pictures. [8, p. 324]

Fig. 1. The title and one of the lots of the Catalogue of the Rudolph Lepke's Auction was held 6-7, Nov.1928 in Berlin.

References

1. Gosudarstvennij Ermitazh. Muzejnija rasprodaji. 1929. Arhivnija dokumenti. Vipusk IV. Chast' Chast' 1. Under the general editorship of M.B. Piotrovsky. Compiler – E.Y. Solomakha. Sankt-Peterburg. Izdatel'stvo Gosudarstvennogo Ermitazha, 2014. P. 10, 17. [Published in Russian]
2. Kantor J.Z. Reality and Socialist Realism: The Hermitage in 1917-1941 / Zvezda. №5 [Published in Russian]
3. Gosudarstvennij Ermitazh. Muzejnija rasprodaji of 1928-1929. Arhivnija dokumenti. Under the general editorship of M.B. Piotrovsky. Compiler – Solomakha E.Y. Sankt-Peterburg. Izdatel'stvo Gosudarstvennogo Ermitazha, 2006. P. 22, 475-492. [Published in Russian]

4. Iljin N., Semenova N. Prodannije sokrovisha Rossii. Moscow. Izdatel'stvo 'Trilistnik', 2000. P. 240. [Published in Russian]
5. Gosudarstvennij Ermitazh. Muzejnija rasprodaji. 1929. Arhivnija dokumenti. Vipusk IV. Chast' 2. Under the general editorship of M.B. Piotrovsky. Compiler – E.Y. Solomakha. Sankt-Peterburg. Izdatel'stvo Gosudarstvennogo Ermitazha, 2014. P. 5 [Published in Russian]
6. Foreign Trade in USSR for 1918 -1940. Moscow, 1960. P. 120. [Published in Russian]
7. Zhukov Y.N. Operatzia "Ermitazh". Moskva. Izdatel'stvo Vagrius, 2005 P. 324 . [Published in Russian]